

An Abstract Description of Learning as a Morphogenetic Process

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Abstract:

This paper describes a mathematical framework for describing learning in terms of convergence to a stable equilibrium point of a Hebbian neural network. It implies that network dynamics can be approximated by a system of diffusion equations, which has stable equilibrium if a particular parameter is large enough. The learned state is identified with the stable equilibrium point. The model suggests that the magnitude of the eigenvalues associated with the system linearised about the fixed point should be directly

related to the slope of an exponential learning curve.

Keywords: *Learning, Morphogenetic model, Mathematical Framework, Hebbian Neural Network, Exponential Learning Curve.*

Introduction

The learning activity is considered a structural transition triggered using an appropriate external stimulus and associated with acquiring a new pattern of behavior (Caianiello, 1961). The first approaches towards defining a system model that shows the learning process date back to Hebb's work (Hebb, 1949).

Several researchers have attempted to answer some learning problems using neural net simulations with a statistical approach (Amari, Yoshida, Kanatani, 1977). Anninos (1972) and Kauffman (1969) have shown that a neural network, composed of some distinct units, admits some stable and unstable equilibrium states; however, such a network is subject to chaotic behavior. This result questions the utility of statistical models: a learning process is not generated by a chaos-order transition (or vice-versa), but it is caused using a transition from a specific type of order to another, and chaos, if reached, can be

considered as a transient instability instead of a permanent behavior (Harth, 1983).

Cohen and Grossberg (1983) have shown, in their studies on continuous learning processes, that it is possible to give a mathematical proof of the Hebb hypothesis in the sense that any external input given to a system of interconnected elements, satisfying the Hebb assumptions, will create a suitable stable spatiotemporal activity pattern. In some trivial cases, determining those patterns is practically impossible.

Easton and Gordon (1984) have shown a simple case where the recurrent inhibition mediated by a modifiable Hebbian synapse does impose stability on the excitatory Hebbian synapse. Conversely, simple inhibitory configurations do not set stability. In general, the inhibitory synapses are not modifiable, but only recurrent inhibition with at least one modifiable synapse in the feedback path can stabilise a Hebbian excitatory synapse. However, self-excitation

alone can sustain a cell assembly when lateral excitatory connections are present.

These considerations suggest, in one way or another, that the learning process should be viewed as equivalent to forming a new stable pattern of activity; this point of view raises many

difficulties and, simultaneously, opens the way to using well-known mathematical methods like those introduced in the so-called "morphogenetic" models (Belintsev, 1983). Such difficulties can be summarized as follows:

1. Which are the objective referents of the stable pattern?
2. How are the stable patterns connected to the external behavior or the abilities learned?
3. How do the stable patterns depend on the external input?
4. Can a learning curve from a morphogenetic model be derived to be compared with experimental data?

The answers to these questions require precise choices of models. The structures of these models provide a means of classifying different learning theories (An der Heiden, 1980). Without facing this problem, we will study in this paper the case in which the hypotheses adopted are:

- a. transition to a stable activity pattern of the distinct units in the network will be identified with the learning process.
- b. the set of external behaviors is in bijective correspondence with the set of spatio-temporal patterns of module activity.
- c. the structure of the stable pattern depends only on the parameter values, driven by a single action of the external input.

These hypotheses do not solve the problem of the precise form of the correspondence law between external behavior and internal activity (Guazzo, 1987a); however, they determine a learning curve whose parameters can be connected to experimental data.

The Model

To transform these hypotheses into a concrete and general morphogenetic learning model, it is necessary to introduce further hypotheses related to the evolution law of module activity and the learning law.

We will adopt N analogic units with real output whose activity x_i ($i=1, \dots, N$) is given by:

$$\frac{dx_i(t)}{dt} = -a_i F(x_i(t - \pi)) + \sum_j w_{ij} F(x_j(t - \pi)) \quad (1)$$

where w_{ij} is the interconnection coefficients, π the synaptic delay, F is a nonlinear (sigmoidal) output function and a_i a suitable decay constant. If we introduce a distinction between excitatory and inhibitory units $x_i^e(t)$ ($i=1, \dots, N_e$) and $x_j^{in}(t)$ ($j=N_e+1, \dots, N$) we can write (1) as:

$$\frac{dx_i^e}{dt} = -a_i F(x_i^e(t - \pi)) + \sum_j w_{ij}^{ee} F(x_j(t - \pi)) + \sum_k w_{ik}^{ei} F(x_k(t - \pi)) \quad (2.a)$$

$$\frac{dx_j^{in}}{dt} = -a_j F(x_j^{in}(t - \pi)) + \sum_l w_{jl}^{ie} F(x_l(t - \pi)) + \sum_k w_{jk}^{ii} F(x_k(t - \pi)) \quad (2.b)$$

where w^{ee} , w^{ei} , w^{ie} , w^{ii} denote, respectively, the excitatory-excitatory, excitatory-inhibitory, inhibitory-excitatory and inhibitory-inhibitory connections.

Now, by using some assumptions used in neurophysiology we can put:

$$w_{jk}^{ii} = 0 \quad (3)$$

and for the other coefficients we will introduce an Hebbian learning law of the type:

$$\frac{dw_{ij}}{dt} = \Gamma x_i(t)x_j(t - \pi) - \Lambda w_{ij} \quad (4)$$

where Γ and Λ are suitable constants. If we now suppose that the w_{ij} are “slow” variables, so that $dw_{ij}/dt = 0$, we will obtain from (4) explicit expression of w_{ij} in terms of $x_i(t)x_j(t - \pi)$. By identifying, for small π , $x_i(t - \pi)$ with $x_i(t)$ and supposing that, for simplicity, excitatory units have zero decay rates and output functions of the type:

$$F(x) = k_1x + k_2x^2 + \dots \quad (5)$$

with zero constant term, we will obtain from (2) equations in $x^e(t)$ and $x^{in}(t)$ if we assume that the system is continuous and at every point there is a module whose activity depends on time and position.

Assuming the activity of each module is independent of its position, i.e.

$$x_i^e = x_j^e = \alpha, \quad x_i^{in} = x_j^{in} = \beta \quad (6)$$

the excitatory activity α and the inhibitory activity β will be described by a system of the type:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = -ak_1\alpha + \alpha^2F(\alpha) + \alpha\beta F(\beta) \\ \frac{d\beta}{dt} = ak_1\beta + \alpha\beta F(\alpha) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where

$$F(y) = k_1\Gamma y / \Lambda \quad (8)$$

By putting:

$$\xi = \alpha - \alpha_0, \quad \eta = \beta - \beta_0 \quad (9)$$

where α_0, β_0 are the equilibrium values corresponding to

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{d\beta}{dt} = 0 \quad (10)$$

we will obtain, by neglecting all terms in ξ, η of order not greater than two or with coefficients containing α_0 (which is to be considered as very small), that the system (7) can be written under the form:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\xi}{dt} = S + \frac{1}{\pi_1}\xi\eta \\ \frac{d\eta}{dt} = r\xi^2 + r\eta \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where S, π_1, r are suitable constants.

Now the spatial dependence can be dealt with, by using a "diffusion" approximation, so that the final form of our system is:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} = D_1 \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{1}{\pi} \xi \eta + S \\ \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial t} = D_2 \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial x^2} + r \xi^2 + r \eta \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where D_1 and D_2 are the diffusion coefficients of the variables ξ and η .

The Exponential Learning Curve

System (12) describes a self-organization process; therefore, a non-homogeneous dissipative structure will appear when some parameters overcome “thresholds”. The equilibrium points of such a system can be found by using a standard procedure (Auchmuty, Nicolis, 1975):

$$\xi_0 = \sqrt[3]{\eta S} \quad (13.a)$$

$$\eta_0 = -\sqrt[3]{(\pi S)^2} \quad (13.b)$$

We find the dispersion equation for the eigenvalues λ using a linear stability analysis. Linearizing system (12) around the fixed point (ξ_0, η_0) yields the eigenvalue equation:

$$\lambda^2 - \lambda \left[2 \left(-B^2 D_1 + \frac{\eta_0}{\pi} \right) (-B^2 D_2 + r) \right] + \left[\left(-B^2 D_1 + \frac{\eta_0}{\pi} \right) (-B^2 D_2 + r) \right]^2 \frac{2\xi_0^2 r}{\pi} = 0 \quad (14)$$

where B is a variable parameter that is determined from external behavior. The fixed point (ξ_0, η_0) is stable if both roots of (14), considered as a quadratic in λ , have a negative real part (Guazzo, 1987b). The bifurcation appears when either the last term is equal to zero or the coefficient of the

λ -term is equal to zero. If the cell activity is independent of position, then a stable critical point is not formed by the bifurcation.

One first interesting consideration about this model is that its behaviour is very different when B is very small from the case where B is very large. In the first case, taking in (14) the limit for $k \rightarrow 0$, we will obtain that the eigenvalues λ are both real, with opposite signs, so, neglecting the spatial dependence, we find that the equilibrium point is a saddle point.

In the second case, when $B \rightarrow \infty$, we will obtain the two eigenvalues:

$$\lambda_1 = -B^2 D_2 \quad (15.a)$$

$$\lambda_2 = -B^2 D_1 \quad (15.b)$$

which are both real and negative so that the equilibrium point is a stable node. Interestingly, the presence of "diffusion" can put the system in

a stable state, so stable learning is possible only when a suitable amount of diffusion is present.

From our model, it is possible to derive a learning curve: namely, the learning can be viewed as a process of relaxation to a stable state which evolves with an $\exp(-\lambda t)$ law and is driven by the higher absolute value of λ . Thus, our learning curve neglects an initial transient will have a behavior of the type:

$$L = L_0 [1 - \exp(-\lambda t)] \quad (16)$$

where L is some quantity, which measures the degree of learning, and L_0 is a suitable constant. The time t is related to the number n of trials, so that (16) could have the usual form of a learning curve:

$$L = L_0 [1 - \exp(-\lambda n)] \quad (17)$$

The slope $S(n)$ of the learning curve is dependent from n and is given by:

$$S(n) = \lambda \exp(-\lambda n) \quad (18)$$

When we apply (18) to experimental data, we could use a best-fitting technique to evaluate λ from experimental data. By approximating (14) to the first order in λ , we will obtain that λ is negative if and only if B^2 is less than the critical value B_c^2 ($B^2 < B_c^2$); the positive solution of the quadratic equation:

$$B^4 D_1 D_2 + B^2 \left(D_1 r - D_2 \frac{\eta_0}{\pi} \right) + \frac{\eta_0 \pi}{r} = 0 \quad (19)$$

is:

$$B_c^2 \cong \frac{|\eta_0| r}{(\pi D_1 r - D_2 \eta_0)} \quad (20)$$

Now, the experimental values of the parameter λ can be compared directly with the model's parameters. Therefore, for critical values of the parameter, either a spatial or a temporal dissipative structure appears.

Conclusions

This model shows that a learning process may exist only if the system can self-organize when the external intensity stimulus overcomes a given threshold. Finally, two types of internal activity, excitatory and inhibitory, are mutually interacting non-linearly. The important thing is that the quantitative features of the self-organization process can be directly compared with the experimental data.

The method reported in this paper could be generalized and extended to other learning models even if derived from different hypotheses from those adopted here. In this paper, it has been shown that it is possible to have quantitative learning theories within the realm of deductive experimental science by linking the self-organisation concept with model hypotheses. It must be remarked, moreover, that some other consequences arising from the model could be verified experimentally: 1) the perturbation frequency, up to a threshold, tends to create an inactivity state of the system; 2) when the stimulus is below a critical threshold, the system loses the equilibrium and, in this case, either goes towards inactivity or originates a chaotic behavior.

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